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ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO ECONOMIC INTEGRATION PROCESSES

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Abstract. This article describes the nature and importance of economic integration processes in the development of the country, scientific theories of processes, stages and models of economic integration, factors influencing integration processes, the integration potential of states, as well as worked out appropriate conclusions.

Keywords: integration, trade, market, competition, model, structure, geoeconomic, factors, regional, cooperation.

Introduction.

The globalization of the world economy is leading to increased interaction between countries in all areas. This, in turn, creates additional opportunities for development and progress, as well as specific threats. In order to effectively use these opportunities and jointly confront threats, it is possible to observe the activation of integration processes at various levels within certain regions. Establishing cooperation with integration structures, along with the effective use of economic opportunities, puts on the agenda the need to solve problems that may arise in this area. In this regard, the following thoughts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev can be cited: “Integrating our economy into the world market and supporting exports is a priority task... We need to transition to an export-oriented economy, form a competitive environment in the domestic market.” In this regard, the integration processes taking place at the global and regional levels cannot fail to have their impact on the security of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the above considerations, it follows that Uzbekistan's participation in any integration processes is primarily driven by national interests, and at the same time, it means that the deterioration of relations with other countries as a result of integration is not allowed.

Currently, when thinking about integration, economic integration is primarily considered. In this context, it is important to note that any interstate integration has two components - economic and political. Since gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been participating in integration processes of various levels.

This article examines scientific approaches to the study of economic integration processes. Based on the above, the relevance of the research work is explained by the following:

- lack of methodological tools for assessing the impact of economic integration processes on the national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- lack of experience (“immunity”) in ensuring the country's economic security in economic integration processes;

- lack of a model for the specialization of national economic sectors in the process of economic integration, etc.

Literature review.

Nowadays, integration processes in the CIS are of interest to many researchers. In particular, T. Börzel, in his scientific research on integration theories and comparative regionalism, focuses on identifying the main patterns in this direction while studying the integration processes taking place within the European region and studying the possibilities of their implementation in other regions. In this case, neofunctional and liberal approaches are taken as the theoretical and methodological basis of the research. According to the scientist, the main driving force of regional economic integration processes is the interconnectedness of countries. At the same time, he puts forward the idea of the special importance of the political factor in the processes of economic integration.

The essence of the integration policy of countries, the factors influencing it, and the approach of Russia, the leading state in the CIS, to the integration processes are reflected in the scientific research of O.V. Bakhlova. According to her scientific analysis, integration in the CIS is carried out more on the basis of the "bloc type", and the countries participating in these processes are primarily seeking to protect their conjunctural interests, rather than achieving common goals. In addition, she tried to substantiate with empirical research that the effectiveness and efficiency of economic integration on the socio-economic situation in countries do not sufficiently meet the requirements of the present day.

The practical significance of O.V. Bakhlova's scientific research is explained, first of all, by the development of scenarios for the development of integration processes in the CIS. In this, the researcher tried to make predictions about how economic integration will develop in various directions and what its results may be. The problems of the impact of integration processes on economic security were analyzed by M. Baidurin in his scientific works. He paid special attention to the study of the theoretical and methodological foundations of integration processes in the context of globalization, issues of ensuring the national interests of countries in these processes, and studied the impact of integration processes on economic security on the example of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU).

The practical significance of M. Baidurin's research is characterized by the following: firstly, a methodology for determining the current state and prospects of integration processes in the CIS space was developed, secondly, the measures taken by the EAEU member states to protect their economic interests within the framework of the structure were analyzed and appropriate proposals were developed in this direction.

On the issues of economic integration processes in the CIS space and their impact on the economic security of countries, such researchers as Sultanova B., Buzrukova G.D., Bolgova I., Nikitina Yu. also expressed their scientific views. In their scientific research, they paid special attention to the issue of the impact of integration on the sovereignty of the country.

The issues of assessing integration processes in the CIS space and characterizing them on the basis of certain economic indicators were covered in the scientific research of E. Vinokurov. In it, the integration of common markets and the convergence of the economies of member states were calculated on the basis of specific indices, problematic situations in this direction were identified and appropriate proposals were developed. In this regard, indicators for studying cooperation in the fields of foreign trade, migration and investment were developed, using which the level of integration in the CIS space was determined.

The importance of E. Vinokurov's scientific research is explained, first of all, by the fact that it is possible to study integration processes on the basis of specific parameters and, based on them, to develop proposals and provide development forecasts.

Scientific research on the issues of studying economic integration using an indicative approach is described in the studies of A. Liebman and F. de Lombarde. In this, they paid attention to the issues of developing indices for assessing interaction in various models of integration.

Researchers have made practical proposals for developing a system of indicators for assessing integration processes in the CIS. Economic integration models have been analyzed in the scientific research of K. Bagdasaryan. The scientist studied regional integration as a specific construction model and described its structure, classifying its distinctive features. The researcher tried to reveal the essence of such concepts as “form”, “depth”, “breadth” and “direction” of integration and developed a generalized structure of the integration model. In general, in the above-mentioned studies, the essence of economic integration, its models, factors influencing the process, indices for their assessment were scientifically studied and proposals were made for their practical application. In addition, the issues of ensuring economic security in the context of economic integration were covered. However, research in this area was carried out in separate studies, and they were not studied within the framework of a single scientific work.

Research methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is the views of theorists of the neoliberal direction, according to which integration is interpreted as the process of forming a single geoeconomic region that includes several states. The study also uses the ideas of the theory of neofunctionalism. According to this theory, the political factor is recognized as having a significant role in integration processes. The methodological basis of the study is a systematic approach, and at the same time, the study uses the methods of comparative analysis and retrospective analysis.

Analysis and results

In the context of economic globalization, increased competition in world markets, and growing tensions between major countries in the international arena, regional economic integration processes are becoming an important factor in the socio-economic development of countries, as well as in achieving their geoeconomic and geopolitical goals. On the one hand, the expansion of economic ties on a global scale creates additional opportunities for socio-economic development of countries, an open economy, healthy competition, a radical improvement in the business and investment climate, the creation of new jobs through the rapid development of the private sector, and the modernization and diversification of industrial production.

The concept of "integration" is derived from the Latin word *integratio* - unification, expansion, integer - whole, single, and implies the unification of parts into a single whole while preserving their characteristics. The concept of integration is widely used across sectors and industries and acquires its own meaning in each case. Therefore, it is given different definitions in different sources. In particular, political integration - the formation of interstate political structures, the formation of common strategic goals and a political legal framework, social integration - the interaction of social strata and groups in society, cultural integration - the strengthening of language, customs and intercultural ties, and economic integration - the establishment of deep and stable cooperation between countries, based on their national interests, on a voluntary basis, with the rational use of available resources, in order to ensure economic development and production competitiveness.

It should be noted that integration is a dynamic process, constantly developing under the influence of internal and external factors. In particular, the process of disintegration (from Latin *de* - “to cancel” + *integratio* - “to unite”) of parts that were previously united into a single whole, for objective or subjective reasons, leads to disintegration (from Latin *de* - “to undo” + *integratio* - “to unite”), while their reunification leads to reintegration (from Latin *re* - “again” + *integratio* - “to unite”). Theorists propose

to study integration simultaneously as both a constantly developing process (dynamic) and a certain state (static).

Economists draw attention to the fact that integration processes operate at different levels and can occur on a global scale (globalization) and between several countries (regional integration). Economic integration at the global level is organized within the framework of the World Trade Organization, regional integration is organized on the basis of agreements aimed at the liberalization of bilateral and multilateral trade between countries and the development of economic relations.

It should be emphasized that today no country in the world can develop without establishing effective relations with other countries. States, based on their political, economic, geopolitical or geoeconomic interests, unite in certain structures and form various integration groups. Currently, more than 50 economic integration associations and about 300 multilateral interstate agreements providing for the liberalization of regional trade are in force in the world. A number of theories have been developed in the study of these processes, in particular, according to representatives of the neoliberal approach, in economic integration a common market is formed on the scale of several countries and the laws of a market economy operate in it, the state ensures compliance with existing laws and regulations and performs a kind of arbiter.

According to representatives of corporatism, transnational corporations, in order to expand their markets, diversify economic activities and liberalize the economic system in countries, encourage relevant state institutions to actively participate in the processes of economic integration. According to neo-Keynesians, when states enter into foreign economic relations with each other, on the one hand, the states joining the integration structure will have to choose the optimal path between the loss of their sovereignty and the obligation to coordinate their economic policies, and on the other hand, based on their national interests, they will have to maintain their economic and political independence. In this case, states create special higher-level bodies in order to achieve general economic efficiency and regulate economic activities and transfer some of their sovereign rights to them. In this case, states, while giving up part of their sovereignty, have the opportunity to use the sovereignty of other integrating states in general. The most important issue here is the degree to which states are willing to collectively exercise their sovereign rights in the economic and political spheres.

Integration processes are an integral part of the globalization of the world economy. They are a qualitatively new form of interstate relations, the ultimate goal of which is to increase the rates of economic growth and ensure the competitiveness of the entire production system. In this context, regional economic integration can be defined as a process (dynamic approach) and a state (static approach) associated with a qualitatively new level of cooperation between states in a given area, strengthening economic ties, mutual exchange of experience and technologies, and the removal of trade, economic, financial and other barriers within the framework of the integration structure. Integration associations can have several forms in terms of their goals and objectives, methods of their implementation, the level of implementation of decisions made within the association, and their impact on trade and economic relations with third countries. Integrating countries should choose a specific integration model based on their goals and capabilities. The integration model is a set of general views on the system of relations, which provides for the formation of close relations between the integration subjects in order to achieve their goals.

Scientists have conventionally divided the models of integration processes in the world into four groups. At the same time, there are different approaches to the question of whether the driving force of integration is economic interest or political ideas. In particular, representatives of the federalist approach emphasize the primary political aspect of integration and describe it as a process of forming federation-

like associations between states. Representatives of neofederalism, who are the successors of this theory, consider the goal of integration to be the creation of a "political community."

The integration model determines the mechanisms and institutional organization of interactions between integrating entities. In this case, the economic efficiency of the integration model depends, first of all, on the extent to which the main economic actors (large businesses, state corporations and transnational companies) penetrate the markets of the countries cooperating within the framework of integration. In addition, the formation of appropriate organizational mechanisms and structures in the conditions of a market economy does not always lead to the fact that economic entities conduct their entrepreneurial activities within the framework of the integration structure, in which they act primarily based on their own economic interests. At the same time, economic entities, acting in their own interests, may cause harm to other partners as a result of failure to fulfill their obligations to achieve common goals.

Based on the levels of economic integration processes, the subjects of integration can be states (official level) and business structures (corporate level). Here, formal institutional mechanisms are formed only in the context of interstate economic integration. The depth of economic relations of integration subjects and the forms of cooperation are the main factors in choosing institutional mechanisms. The business structures participating in the integration process, in turn, consist of national business entities and transnational companies (TNCs).

At this point, various factors influence the processes of global economic integration, and they can be conditionally divided into two groups:

Factors affecting integration processes

Economic development (characteristics of the regional economy); Specialization of the production structure (development of the main production areas); Infrastructure (development of transport system);

- The standard of living of the population (level of social development, labor force assessment).
- The objectives of participation in the integration processes of the above entities can be conditionally expressed as follows:
 - national business entities: expanding trade networks and increasing the volume of production;
 - TNC: obtaining cheap resources and raising the level of profit by achieving a monopoly position;
 - states: ensuring socio-economic development, satisfying geopolitical and geoeconomic interests.

Reciprocity of the economic potential of the participating countries is of great importance in the formation of the interstate economic integration model. Economically, the obvious superiority of one country over others in itself prepares the ground for it to play the role of a specific "locomotive" in this structure. This, in turn, leads to the fact that other economically weaker states within the framework of an integration structure fall under the sphere of influence of the leading country. The initial stage of the process of interstate economic integration involves the conclusion of bilateral and multilateral agreements providing for various advantages in mutual trade. Within the framework of a free trade area, customs duties and non-tariff barriers to mutual trade are reduced or eliminated, and free transit is ensured.

Integration potential is a set of natural, production, labor, financial, intellectual and other resources of the member states of the integration structure, the joint use of which is characterized by greater efficiency than when used individually. This factor allows the integration structure to achieve a competitive advantage over other states and structures on a global scale.

The factor of having a common border among the member states is of great importance for the effective use of the above-mentioned integration potential. Based on this factor, some scientists classify integration structures as follows: regional (cooperation of states with common borders); international (cooperation of countries that do not have a common border, but are located on the same continent); transcontinental (cooperation of countries on different continents).

According to this classification, the presence of a common border in the formation of certain forms of integration structures (customs union, common market) is an important condition for their full-fledged functioning. The fact that these factors differ fundamentally from each other across countries, the desire of states to protect their geoeconomic and geopolitical interests, and political and economic changes taking place on a global scale indicate that regional economic integration processes in the same area can occur at different degrees and speeds. This, in turn, requires the development of new approaches to the study of economic integration. In this regard, theorists are currently introducing the concept of “comparative regionalism”. According to this approach, in regional integration processes, economic relations with countries outside the region, interdependence in the field of ensuring security, and the desire to maintain political stability in countries are more important than the factor of economic interdependence within the region.

Conclusions and suggestions

Given that economic integration processes play an important role in the socio-economic development and political life of countries, the issue of participation in regional economic integration structures should be resolved, first of all, based on the national interests of states;

➤ The complex and dynamic nature of regional economic integration processes has led to the formation of various scientific approaches to their study, which creates the need to scientifically study this phenomenon and develop practical proposals based on the most appropriate theories, taking into account the factors of space and time;

➤ One of the most pressing issues in economic integration processes is the problem of the transfer of certain sovereign rights by states to supranational organizations;

Uzbekistan's efforts to further develop trade and economic relations with neighboring countries put on the agenda the issue of developing well-thought-out principles and forms of cooperation with economic integration structures within the region. This necessitates a comprehensive and detailed study of the theoretical aspects of the problem.

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